

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICACY OF CONSERVATIVE THERAPY IN PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH HYPERTROPHIC CARDIOMYOPATHY

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The study included 30 patients aged from 19 to 72 years (mean age 64.2 ± 13.4 years). Men accounted for 61% of patients ($n = 22$), while women constituted 39% ($n = 14$).

Objective:

To evaluate survival, as well as the dynamic changes in instrumental and clinical parameters, in patients diagnosed with non-obstructive hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) receiving conservative therapy.

Materials and Methods:

The study included 30 patients aged from 19 to 72 years (mean age 64.2 ± 13.4 years). Men accounted for 61% of patients ($n = 22$), while women constituted 39% ($n = 14$). The diagnosis of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy was established based on echocardiographic findings, primarily interventricular septal hypertrophy. The assessment included echocardiographic parameters, functional tests, and quality of life evaluation. The follow-up period was 2 years.

Results:

After 2 years of follow-up, the thickness of the interventricular septum increased by 12.9%, from 21.27 ± 6.12 mm to 24.02 ± 6.7 mm. The posterior wall thickness of the left ventricle increased by 12.2%, from 12.77 ± 3.25 mm to 14.34 ± 4.79 mm. Left ventricular myocardial mass increased from 362.98 ± 146.3 g to 385.5 ± 139.3 g. These structural changes resulted in a 17% increase in the mean pressure gradient across the left ventricular outflow tract, from 25.31 ± 18.3 mmHg to 29.65 ± 19.03 mmHg, with a maximum recorded gradient of 80 mmHg. A 4.2% decrease in left ventricular ejection fraction was observed, declining from $64.19 \pm 13.4\%$ to $61.5 \pm 16.36\%$. Despite the unfavorable echocardiographic changes, the six-minute walk test distance remained unchanged at 255.52 ± 55.8 m. During the 2-year follow-up period, 3 patients (8.3%) died due to cardiovascular causes. Permanent pacemaker implantation due to complete atrioventricular block was required in 2 patients (5.56%).

ABSTRACT

To evaluate survival, as well as the dynamic changes in instrumental and clinical parameters, in patients diagnosed with non-obstructive hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) receiving conservative therapy.

Conclusion:

Over a two-year follow-up period, patients with non-obstructive hypertrophic cardiomyopathy demonstrated negative echocardiographic remodeling despite conservative therapy. These findings were associated with a high risk of disease-related mortality and an increased need for permanent pacemaker implantation.

